

Circle packing inside a regular hexadecagon: supplemental material

Paolo Amore

Facultad de Ciencias, CUICBAS, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
paolo@ucol.mx

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular hexadecagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular hexadecagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular hexadecagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexadecagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.495149721732	0.503179917312	41	0.136082978898	0.779133175374
3	0.457221451812	0.643568348049	42	0.134590794263	0.780728849295
4	0.410879308247	0.692960944305	43	0.13320677166	0.782963085575
5	0.36479599204	0.682795021344	44	0.131782751937	0.78413356879
6	0.331170661062	0.675266469781	45	0.130457611226	0.785907770722
7	0.327408427053	0.770012848459	46	0.129031520707	0.785904342028
8	0.298219404666	0.730099430866	47	0.127962372434	0.789737298426
9	0.275276047043	0.699841320741	48	0.126752687057	0.79136312944
10	0.259076416135	0.688772797312	49	0.125215926092	0.788379721442
11	0.251164419238	0.712080580393	50	0.12430964684	0.792866182698
12	0.24495058361	0.738853658686	51	0.123031472283	0.792178120832
13	0.23279737803	0.722969118072	52	0.122093713681	0.795445036428
14	0.228751748884	0.751756352995	53	0.120820011942	0.793914700027
15	0.218093322591	0.732143518417	54	0.1202950574	0.801880315118
16	0.21366197961	0.749539808678	55	0.11961526981	0.807525346997
17	0.205917004872	0.739696513691	56	0.117825103758	0.797781413249
18	0.202733212758	0.759176114705	57	0.116957820523	0.800117214325
19	0.20211579842	0.796479035794	58	0.115827982443	0.798500517492
20	0.192692071372	0.762040250869	59	0.114878920792	0.799011317381
21	0.188035399172	0.761936454367	60	0.114145922021	0.802217767479
22	0.181548742791	0.74409673268	61	0.113537399228	0.806915287639
23	0.178389000729	0.751076556752	62	0.111906704129	0.796753765832
24	0.175006175983	0.754289769404	63	0.111131002358	0.798419688153
25	0.172285439119	0.761478037743	64	0.110136467598	0.796640690986
26	0.169380978228	0.765460608909	65	0.109509644715	0.799904834682
27	0.16733389968	0.775803713169	66	0.108787915996	0.801540507375
28	0.165343666181	0.785513010288	67	0.107839782421	0.799563635006
29	0.162161207473	0.782550119394	68	0.107112128706	0.800583137879
30	0.160554722034	0.793574393511	69	0.106390896992	0.801453365268
31	0.156347782078	0.777616323407	70	0.105728138278	0.802970213166
32	0.153818259145	0.776937327154	71	0.105065643863	0.804266587001
33	0.152117848281	0.783600153329	72	0.104379962641	0.804983531738
34	0.149199102273	0.776661115439	73	0.103882729616	0.808406488148
35	0.147680248226	0.783308964466	74	0.103429372897	0.812343533844
36	0.146379246751	0.791556176233	75	0.102347737052	0.806191060011
37	0.145538331458	0.804223450026	76	0.10165128725	0.805859968845
38	0.141827451649	0.78437622404	77	0.100959722102	0.805391873564
39	0.139984857939	0.784236324004	78	0.100435933083	0.807408031497
40	0.138529233057	0.787704045823	79	0.099734654905	0.806379530652

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexadecagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.099261915795	0.808864021143	121	0.0812514835404	0.81972502587
81	0.0988085524198	0.811510825285	122	0.0808577714309	0.818509247494
82	0.0983679465214	0.814219104473	123	0.0804002140289	0.815905285026
83	0.0980138920032	0.818226586971	124	0.0801456823454	0.817338905268
84	0.0974953605627	0.819346137402	125	0.0798097444126	0.817037665735
85	0.096798288478	0.817286843467	126	0.0795498532994	0.818218955357
86	0.0958797965162	0.811283949032	127	0.079257036921	0.818652532935
87	0.0952388419096	0.809781198971	128	0.0790698091635	0.821204983078
88	0.0946014957089	0.80816288796	129	0.078716725924	0.820245732719
89	0.0941367499408	0.809335578211	130	0.078436619018	0.820731889064
90	0.0936190533138	0.809452231969	131	0.0781073397313	0.820115865318
91	0.0931047405418	0.809478290409	132	0.0778383119309	0.820693462789
92	0.0926006692489	0.809536255015	133	0.0775919773508	0.821685276731
93	0.0922507051635	0.812161807923	134	0.0773202556221	0.82207527377
94	0.0917018500011	0.811155791338	135	0.0770417017121	0.822253494031
95	0.0912917438514	0.812469069491	136	0.076770777914	0.822528616
96	0.0908167141977	0.81249936044	137	0.0764998883657	0.822739588362
97	0.0903839383054	0.81315714294	138	0.0762222852148	0.822741192588
98	0.0899975204631	0.814530571875	139	0.0758985143511	0.821677841677
99	0.0896525629048	0.816546343338	140	0.0755891261692	0.820855874175
100	0.0892210152157	0.816873008934	141	0.0753387638738	0.821251769262
101	0.088710361401	0.815624562349	142	0.0750905195836	0.821634729959
102	0.0882306315892	0.814815295851	143	0.0748816546917	0.822824335718
103	0.0878189359907	0.815142977911	144	0.0746100278653	0.822578059759
104	0.0874193837511	0.815584654467	145	0.0743002500554	0.821426629742
105	0.0870937684328	0.817304121168	146	0.0740707998556	0.821991165184
106	0.0867431530762	0.818458191017	147	0.073898176191	0.823768156921
107	0.0862468428526	0.816752392564	148	0.0736755168998	0.824381663862
108	0.0858100245513	0.816056133052	149	0.0734716114351	0.825364193278
109	0.0853236940539	0.814302977187	150	0.0732569053656	0.826054347638
110	0.085042188031	0.816360083299	151	0.0731167836967	0.82838329174
111	0.0846408369906	0.816024320629	152	0.0728177850583	0.827063285433
112	0.0843186016565	0.81711849183	153	0.0726006346592	0.827546660373
113	0.0840154467123	0.818496733175	154	0.0723675860584	0.827616457974
114	0.0836869233374	0.819294953855	155	0.0721128158102	0.827135824384
115	0.0833686315014	0.82020688526	156	0.0719306099087	0.828270719984
116	0.0830635131971	0.821294294689	157	0.0716808208706	0.827800754215
117	0.0827677843831	0.822486439258	158	0.0714697251544	0.828173893283
118	0.0824485690765	0.823130089978	159	0.0711907009945	0.826920746657
119	0.0821314533978	0.823732503092	160	0.0709671967421	0.826904792516
120	0.0817246524217	0.822446459802	161	0.0707130751435	0.826124589977

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexadecagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0703785312163	0.823409053085	182	0.0668096216168	0.83362290172
163	0.0701874827552	0.823999908222	183	0.0665555022764	0.831838937606
164	0.0699958268219	0.824533621178	184	0.0662786265402	0.829440139314
165	0.0698152161529	0.825285744188	185	0.0660958807603	0.829355524296
166	0.0696439366775	0.826218541835	186	0.0659431726294	0.829989971816
167	0.0694400749157	0.826336730876	187	0.0658219670288	0.831387604112
168	0.0692375301185	0.826442496595	188	0.0656113284486	0.830492541732
169	0.0690735188197	0.827427768031	189	0.0655105516175	0.83234723649
170	0.068884900772	0.827784367864	190	0.0653478806938	0.832600832959
171	0.068743433598	0.829237199928	191	0.0652524313608	0.834539676868
172	0.0684750715357	0.827587002439	192	0.0650488519652	0.833682578634
173	0.0683175635271	0.828573552622	193	0.0649311200999	0.834993940161
174	0.0681144444008	0.828414916815	194	0.0647675937366	0.835098069455
175	0.0679563600784	0.829313034867	195	0.0645810066305	0.834573242839
176	0.0677806917213	0.829745462597	196	0.0644028750093	0.834231926961
177	0.067598991006	0.829992023641	197	0.0642611309527	0.834801422493
178	0.0674629839066	0.831325916726	198	0.0640868541167	0.834494199856
179	0.0672193166102	0.829968179014	199	0.0639429592941	0.834946723551
180	0.0670709304017	0.830924170042	200	0.0637517605631	0.834131623068
181	0.0669571310676	0.832707495779			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexadecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

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References

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